

Open science skills and competences for OPUSH

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Summary

Open Science Skills and competences are crucial for practising Citizen Science in the OPUSH project. The paper gives an overview of skills and competences relevant for OPUSH project members to foster the goals of sustainable urban development and life-long learning through Citizen Social Science experimentation.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/ Acronym	Description
CRIS	Current research information systems
CS	Citizen science (including citizen social science)
GDPR	General data protection regulation
GLAM	Galleries, libraries, archives and museums
IPR	Intellectual property rights
OPUSH	Open urban sustainability hubs
OS	Open science
SDG	Sustainable development goal

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Open science skills and competences for OPUSH

The objective of this paper is to outline open science (OS) and citizen science (CS) skills and competences that are relevant in the context of the Open Sustainability Hubs (OPUSH) project. The paper will first discuss the principles and standards of OS with special consideration for CS and life-long learning processes. The mentioned principles and standards include guidelines from UNESCO (2021), European Commission (2017), the LIBER Citizen Science working group (2021) and the OPUSH Code of Conduct (2022). In addition, European and transnational literature was reviewed to find relevant competences and skills for OPUSH to practice OS. The review focused on the topics of sustainable urban transformation and CS experimentation. The following five areas of skills and competences emerged from the review:

1. Project organisation and management
2. Scientific research
3. Open knowledge and data literacy
4. Transdisciplinary collaboration and communication
5. Digital interaction and structured content creation

The paper is, therefore, designed as a checklist for OPUSH and other CS projects' team members, especially researchers and librarians, to successfully prepare and implement CS projects in different national and institutional contexts.

The different areas can overlap themselves. They cannot always be precisely assigned to particular institutions or persons. The application of skills and competences should take place project-specifically and accordingly to the focus and methodology of the research, the involved partners, the local context etc. Within the paper a focus on area 4 "collaboration and communication" is apparent. This area connects especially to skills and competences necessary for practising CS.

1. Principles of open science and citizen science

1.1 Relevance of OS and CS skills and competences for OPUSH

In the context of the OPUSH project, OS is defined as "the opening up of knowledge and knowledge services for a broader and heterogeneous audience, which is more and more facilitated by the help of digital tools, but however goes along with a necessity of a broader change at the individual and the institutional level (OPUSH 2022a). Therefore, OS is a fairly broad field of action addressing specific skills and competences that might be outside of the scope of traditional research. OPUSH aims to make knowledge on sustainable development and transformative action more visible and traceable, and to empower local communities by granting permanent access to open knowledge ecosystems. Thereby, the project enhances the role and capacity of libraries within OS and through CS as drivers of sustainable development.

The field of urban transformation is particularly characterized by a very heterogeneous landscape of actors and dynamic multi-layered processes that overlap and influence each other. Urban space and urban development are a multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary field of research. A multitude of disciplines and sub-disciplines (as

well as inter- and transdisciplinary research teams and non-academics) deal with space-related issues and specific research approaches. Opening up this fluid landscape of actors and knowledge to citizens is the central goal of the OPUSH project. Therefore, the implementation of CS as a process aimed at inclusive research and sustainable urban transformation requires specific skills and competences within the field of OS.

1.2 Open science principles for OPUSH

1.2.1 Principles following the OPUSH Code of Conduct

One of the OS aims is to establish research data that is “Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR)” (European Commission, 2017, 14). The OPUSH code of conduct specifies the FAIR criteria in the project context and imposes obligations for every project member since all partners will produce data through OS and especially by CS experimentation (OPUSH, 2022b, 5).

Findable: All data generated within the projects scope will be available as open access publications (e.g. free of charge, free internet access) to support scientific communication and education as well as their availability for the public. Participants in OPUSH are proactively encouraged to co-author subject-relevant open access publications and to join processes which support data availability for the general public (OPUSH, 2022b, 5).

Accessible: To the extent possible, project staff ensure the accessibility of digital and physical infrastructure - from websites and software to buildings and workplaces - for citizens and other stakeholders (OPUSH, 2022b, 7).

Interoperable (open data): Data, tools and documents produced within OPUSH will be labelled with open license as far as possible, and this is visible in the Data Management Plan. All metadata will be published under a Creative Commons license (or corresponding open license) to make it usable and reproducible for third parties (OPUSH, 2022b, 11).

Reusable (open source): IT applications (as software or code) used in OPUSH should - dependent on the available resources - be based on open source software for better re-usability and transparency of data and project specific knowledge (OPUSH, 2022b, 11).

1.2.2 Principles following UN-framework for recommendation on open science

UNESCO (2021, 17) specifies the mentioned FAIR-principles for OS and adds the following values addressing especially CS experimentation and sustainability:

Equity: OS enables fair sharing of scientific data and equal access to educational resources for scientists and citizens “regardless of location, nationality, race, age, gender, income, socio-economic circumstances, career stage, discipline, language, religion, disability, ethnicity or migratory status, or any other grounds” (UNESCO, 2021, 17).

Diversity and inclusiveness: OS support diverse knowledge practices and research foci by considering the diversity of scientific communities, the public and knowledge

stakeholders beyond usual scientific institutions to involve local communities and social stakeholders. (UNESCO, 2021, 17)

The OPUSH project targets a variety of knowledge sources by addressing urban transformation by a wide range of topics, focussing on environmental and social justice in the context of sustainable development. But also, by practising CS experimentation in diverse settings under the cooperation with local stakeholders. One central pillar for the project is the integration of diverse research communities through the cooperation of universities (research units, research libraries, research focused classes) with the civil society (citizens), the city administration, practice partners in urban development, GLAM institutions and the integration of urban knowledge infrastructures. The following UNESCO (2021, 19) principles are relevant for the integration of these goals, enabling the practices and ideals of OS:

Responsibility: The openness of science implies greater responsibility for all actors involved. Research should therefore be associated with sensitivity to diverse interest, attentiveness to social and ecological impacts, intellectual probity and consideration of ethical standards. (UNESCO, 2021, 18)

Collaboration: Collaboration between disciplines, social actors and marginalised groups should be established at all levels of the project to find solutions to societal challenges (UNESCO, 2021, 18).

The OPUSH project operates in diverse geographical, lingual and spatial contexts and considers the SDGs as a driving thematic direction. In this context, the following principles are relevant:

Flexibility: OS considers that there is a wide spectrum of “pathways of transition” (UNESCO, 2021, 19) to uphold the mentioned principles and values.

Sustainability: Sustainable OS should establish long-term practices, services and infrastructures. OS infrastructures should be managed and financed on the basis of “essentially not-for-profit and long-term vision [s]” (UNESCO, 2021, 19).

1.2.3 Citizen science and life-long learning as open science standards in OPUSH

The project-team has a common understanding of the role of CS as broadly referring “to the active engagement of the general public in scientific research tasks” (Vohland et al, 2021, 7) Furthermore, CS can be used to establish a process of lifelong learning among all stakeholders involved, as exemplified in Kloetzer et al 2021 (Fig. 1)

Citizen science: The OPUSH project focusses on CS as a set of methodologies to open up the research cycle, from the research design to the interpretation of data and call for actions. In OPUSH, there exists a deep synergetic and symbiotic relationship between CS and OS, aligned with the contents of the DITO Policy Report (DITOs consortium, 2017). In this frame, research data are co-produced and collectively interpreted with the citizen scientists, thus building a shared data narrative, allowing a collective discussion with scientists and policy-makers. Visualizations of urban digital twins and the potential for human-computer interfaces - for example in hubs - can

support CS and OS and enable collaborations by finding a common language and reducing complexity.

Figure 1: Learning in Citizen Science (Kloetzer et al, 2021)

Life-long learning: OPUSH strives for an alignment of life-long learning including researchers, library staff and staff members of knowledge infrastructures and knowledge hubs, but also citizens and a diversity of stakeholders involved in urban transformation. It constitutes a comprehensive approach of learning at every stage of life with the objective of adapting societal change. Within OS, life-long learning is not reduced to an exclusive target group. At this stage of the paper, the focus is on the qualification of researchers and university-library staff, as the skills required for practitioners (e.g. city administrations) will be considered separately in the further research process.

2. Skills and competences for OPUSH

2.1 Differentiation of skills and competences

The literature is partly unclear in the differentiation between skills and competences for practising OS. Hoffmann et al (2022, 16) define skills as a part of competences and include hereby different definitions that are common in Anglo-American and German scientific literature. The development of competences is for them a crucial subject to “an interplay of knowledge, skills/aptitude and attitude“ (Hoffmann et al, 2022, 16). The paper therefore includes skills as well as competences mentioned in literature and summarises them in five areas. To exemplify their implementation, tools and/or methods are added for each area.

The LIBER Open Science Roadmap (Ayrís et al, 2018, 12) defines seven **focus areas for libraries** to work on a fully support of OS: Scholarly publishing; FAIR Data; Research Infrastructures & the EOSC; Metrics & Rewards; Open Science Skills; Research Integrity and CS. Further, the European Commission (2017, 22) designs three key **competences for researchers** to embed OS and establish lifelong learning: Digital competences; Learning to learn; Social and civic competences. **The paper brings together both approaches and connects them directly to the principles of OS mentioned above.** Two areas necessary for effective and successful scientific project implementation expand this framework: project organisation and management and scientific research. On this basis skills and competences out of sustainability guidelines for OS or European commission frameworks have been added to develop an OPUSH-specific framework. (Fig. 2)

Figure 2: Interaction between OS-principles and the five areas of skills/ competences for an OPUSH-specific framework (Own illustration)

2.2 Area 1: Project organisation and management

Area 1 refers to competences and skills for organisation and management of project-internal structures and their consequent establishment during the projects process. Organisation and management can be regarded as “general competences for advancing sustainability and transformations” (Bianchi, 2020, 17).

Skills and/or competences:

Project management: scheduling regular work and evaluation meetings, soliciting feedback from team members (Thuermer et al, 2022, 34); distributing materials; scheduling and moderating meetings (Shirk et al, 2012, 7)

Leadership: responsive leading of project members, wise and compassionate decision-making, mindfulness about the implementation of the project's goals and planned methods (Trad 2019, in Bianchi 2020, 22)

Teamwork: collaborating in decision-making (Trad 2019, in Bianchi 2020, 22), collaboratively working on the projects content by using effectively share of works

Interpersonal communication: building trust among team members and in scientific work itself through empathy; mindfulness and social learning (Pacis et al, 2020, in Bianchi 2020, 22)

Generic communication: clear and respectful communication of tasks and content; implementing digital and non-digital communication skills; ability to work in multi-lingual settings

Stakeholder and community-management: fostering stakeholder engagement and collaboration (Bianchi 2020: 22) (see Area 4: Transdisciplinary Collaboration and Communication)

Co-evaluation: evaluating citizens' experience and impact made by co-production and co-evaluation of scientific findings

Tools and/or methods that can be helpful in developing the above-mentioned skills and/or support their application:

- Educational and management trainings
- Educational plan and trainings
- Team-building events and feedback sessions
- Communication workshops and trainings

2.3 Area 2: Scientific research

The implementation of CS-projects in OPUSH is subject to the principles of scientific research. Not only from non-university actors, but also from scientists' special skills and competences are needed. Area 2 includes skills and competences to establish and mediate scientific standards during the projects process. Especially in practising CS scientific research relies on a co-application of scientific skills and competences during the whole research cycle (preparation, co-design, co-production, co-reflection, transformation). For example, the co-production of a scientific paper with citizens and other cooperation partners. The understanding of scientific concepts and its relevance for society and ones' own daily life, fosters engagement in and reflection of science-related issues and ideas. An availability to join discussions on science and technology through CS can be achieved (Queiruga-Dios et al, 2020, 3).

Skills and/or competences:

Problem identification: identifying and specifying scientific questions guiding political decision making (Queiruga-Dios et al, 2020, 3)

Phenomena explanation: addressing evidence-based scientific arguments and making reasonable conclusions, presenting a coherent perspective adapting scientific arguments (Queiruga-Dios et al, 2020, 3)

Methodological frameworks: developing a theoretical and methodological framework of applied mixed-methods, qualitative and quantitative research (and their combination); designing and implementing a validation method, carefully embedding methods into the urban context (Queiruga-Dios et al, 2020, 3)

Methodological adaptation: adapting and reshaping of scientific methodologies without loss of data-quality to make them accessible for non-scientists (Queiruga-Dios et al, 2020, 3)

Diverse sources: actively advocating for ethical trade-offs regarding grey literature, relevant knowledge beyond scientific and public databases (esp. in urban development, accessing relevant, up-to-date knowledge is challenging)

Interpretation and evaluation: using structured concepts and the underlying methodological frameworks for differentiated results (Queiruga-Dios et al, 2020, 3)

Tools and/or methods that can be helpful in developing the above-mentioned skills and/or to support their application:

- Guidelines for CS research (see a comprehensive list of guidelines in OPUSH D2.1 “OS and urban transformation landscape analysis”)

2.4 Area 3: Open knowledge and data literacy

The careful handling of data generated in OPUSH is highly relevant for the projects progress. Project members must have access to the original data to be able to respond to certain possible questions and scenarios, e.g. affecting the validation of the data and their statutory requirements. (OPUSH, 2022b, 9) Open Access Publishing and Data Management Skills form a rapidly developing field of competence, not only for a special group of scientists and library staff that cover a. o. the handling and development of different CRIS (Current Research Information System) according to the requirements as defined by euroCRIS and (integrated) institutional or discipline-specific or other European repositories or the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) building process as well as discipline-specific e-research methods. (European Commission 2017, 17) Libraries can use these skills to design an ethical and legal framework for co-production of scientific knowledge and involvement of citizen scientists. (LIBER Citizen Science Working Group, 2021, 16)

Data literacy skills refer to a wide range of discipline specific competences that can be summarized as the competency of handling data (Hoffmann et al, 2022, 38). Different models of data librarianship, data stewardship etc., discussed currently, are not referred to in this report because there are no standards agreed upon until now. Recently the Skills4EOSC project has started a standardisation process for key skills and competences with the aim to enable researchers, research support staff, and stakeholders to fulfil the OS expectations of the EOSC (Whyte et al, 2023).

Skills and/or competences according to the research life cycle and research data:

Data generation and collection process: making the data collection process accessible, understandable and GDPR-compliant

Data evaluation and cleansing: analysing, comparing and critically evaluating the credibility and reliability of (digital) data (European Commission, 2017, 17); anonymising or pseudonymising data; cleansing of datasets (e.g. by OpenRefine, R, Python) to guarantee data quality

Data mining: collating, annotating and documenting big data sets and proper data mining (LIBER Citizen Science Working Group 2021, 16); knowing about existing repositories and their usage (European Commission 2017, 17); knowing about generation of qualitative data

Data visualization: interpreting and visualizing data (e.g. for digital twins)

Integration and re-elaboration: modifying, enhancing and integrating information into an existing body of knowledge to support the creation of new, original and relevant content; understanding Copyright and Creative Commons or similar licences to apply to data and digital content (LIBER Citizen Science Working Group 2021, 18)

Metadata creation: coding; using taxonomies and ontologies (LIBER Citizen Science Working Group 2021, 16)

Implementation of FAIR principles: FAIRifying (meta)data, ensuring machine-actionability of data; applying standards; choosing FAIR repositories (David et al, 2020)

Data publishing: publishing datasets and research findings, raw data; documenting intended and implemented analyses as well as creation processes of data (Thuermer et al, 2022, 48); knowing about long-term accessibility of data

Derive data action: establishing data-based decisions in an institution and raising awareness of the evaluation process behind data generation and the resources used (e.g. physical energy) (Schueller et al, 2019, 36)

Tools and/or methods that can be helpful in developing the above-mentioned skills and/or support their application:

- Data Management Plan (OPUSH, 2022b, 10)
- Project web page with clear visible links to external sources (Roman et al, 2020)
- Data Quality Assurance Template to evaluate possible causes of low quality in data, and to create and measure ad hoc indicators (Thuermer et al, 2022, 44)
- Data Quality Resource Compendium as guidance document for quality control in CS projects (Thuermer et al, 2022, 44)
- FAIRness Literacy: The Achilles' Heel of Applying FAIR Principles (2020)
- Legal Compliance Guidelines for Researchers: A Checklist (Sguanga et al, 2022)
- 10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research (Arguillas et al, 2022)
- LIBER Citizen Science Working Group 2021 (2021, 22)

- Data Ethics Toolkit (Cooper et al, 2022)

2.4 Area 4: Transdisciplinary collaboration and communication

One challenge for the OPUSH project is the communication within a broad landscape of actors and the variety of parallel stages of communication. Interactions and co-operations with industrial partners and utilities are endorsed through the European Commission and supported with diverse structural measures. For the practice of CS, the qualified participation of and collaboration with citizens and volunteers is of high relevance in order to arouse and maintain the interest of large groups. These interactions require a consideration of sensitive issues that may occur through partnerships, such as conflicts of interest, which, as a general statement and from the perspective of good scientific practice, have to be avoided. (OPUSH, 2022b, 16; Thuermer et al, 2022, 60)

OPUSH is addressing the higher education community and therein academic libraries (in this case as a service actor and knowledge infrastructure connecting and being related to citizens), professional researchers and urban practitioners to enable CS experimentation. This requires a high degree of sensitivity in communication and an open critical discourse on the advantages and disadvantages of transparency and knowledge claims. Therefore, area 4 is especially important for the OPUSH project in the view of CS to enable interaction and cooperation with other people (Hoffmann et al, 2022, 27). It addresses the goals of community sustainability and a diversity of involved actors. The skills and/or competences include the capacity for a constructive, effective, trustful and meaningful communication. (Hoffmann et al, 2022, 28) Building trust among the partners, including citizens, through the best possible understanding and transparency is essential for the success of multi-stakeholder projects.

Skills and/or competences:

Science-related mediation: explaining the methods used for the right target audience, reflecting people's everyday lives and pointing out the objective's relevance to their location, culture or social environment (Ruefenacht et al, 2021, 478); presenting results in a simple and short manner for inexperienced citizens, lay people and heterogeneous groups

Project mediation: clearly formulating the project framework (goals, problems, messages) for addressing participants' concerns, recognizing motivating factors such as the opportunity to do something meaningful (Thuermer et al, 2022, 26, 28); using appropriate communication to reach target groups (Thuermer et al, 2022, 49)

System-, process- and strategic-thinking

- Constructively combining diverse interests and knowledge and achieving joint action (Hoffmann et al, 2022, 28); involving other institutes and organisations (Thuermer et al, 2022, 25)
- Collectively analysing complex systems across different domains and scales (local to global); considering cascading effects, inertia, feedback loops and other systemic features related to sustainability issues (Wiek et al, 2011, 207)

- Strategically designing and implementing interventions and transformative governance strategies towards sustainability (Wiek et al, 2011, 211)

Community sustainability

- Considering that projects often attract the most participants at the beginning of the project implementation or before the project actually starts (Thuermer et al, 2022, 60)
- Actively approaching people who could or should be involved (Thuermer et al, 2022, 24); designing methods to include personal support structures and relationship-building, designing time and technology accessibility for participants (Hoffmann et al, 2022, 32)
- Considering to give volunteers freedom in the organizational structure to explore their own interests and develop own ideas (Thuermer et al, 2022, 26)
- Communicating continuously and in iterative loops to demonstrate the usefulness of participation (Ruefenacht et al, 2021, 476)

Diversity

- Active listening and sensitivity to the diversity of people's motivations and abilities; considering existing relationships and community-identified problems as motivators for participants (Ruefenacht et al, 2021, 476)
- Considering the intersectionality of concerns (class, gender, disability etc.) that people may bring into or motivate to participate the project
- Grasping specific feelings and perceptions of people working in an unfamiliar context, openness and willingness for self-reflection and learning (Ruefenacht et al, 2021, 476)
- Integrating concepts of equity (needs-based approach) and equality (avoiding discrimination) into the research process, creating favourable and accessible conditions for the inclusion of persons with disabilities (Ruefenacht et al, 2017, 489)

Tools and/or methods that can be helpful in developing the above-mentioned skills and/or support their application:

- Simple and clear manuals, written in plain and inclusive language
- Diversity guidelines (Thuermer et al, 2022, 25)
- Traditional media channels, including journalists, word of mouth (Ruefenacht et al 2021, 476; Thuermer et al, 2022, 25)
- Mailing lists, newsletters (Thuermer et al, 2022, 25)
- Social media, simple websites, surveys (Thuermer et al, 2022, 25)
- Simple apps, vlogs, podcasts, graphics, charts, audio clips (Ruefenacht et al, 2021, 476)
- Visualization in virtual and/or augmented reality
- Storytelling, creative writing, rhetoric classes (Hoffmann et al, 2022)
- Using stakeholder matrices to ensure inclusion of all perspectives (LIBER Citizen Science Working Group 2021, 9; Magalhães et al, 2022)

2.6 Area 5: Digital interaction and structured content creation

Digital content creation skills are becoming increasingly important not only for dissemination purposes. In the context of the OPUSH project, digital skills are needed to ensure “autonomous, sensible and responsible use of digital technologies” (LIBER Digital Skills Working Group 2020, 4) by researchers and citizens joining social science experimentations.

Skills and/or competences:

Digital data retrieval: filtering, organising and storing data or information when browsing and searching in digital environments (Vuorikari et al, 2016, 9)

Digital data development: creating and editing digital content in different formats (LIBER Citizen Science Working Group 2021), using (digital) software for online content, manuals or newsletters (visual design, video) and interactive collaborative visualisation in VR and AR

Data Programming: setting up a web-page to share results and other information if applicable

Interaction: sharing data and digital content to act as intermediary; using referencing and attribution practices; collaborating through digital technologies for co-creation of resources and knowledge (e.g. through open publications, existing repositories, new open publication strategies, the use of VR and AR as well as human-computer interaction in hubs); careful handling of produced data; awareness of public appearance by appropriate use of digital communication channels for a given context (Vuorikari et al, 2016, 8)

Netiquette: mindfulness for norms of behaviour while using digital technologies, considering cultural and generational diversity in digital environments (Vuorikari et al, 2016, 8)

Tools and/or methods that can be helpful in developing the above-mentioned skills and/or support their application:

- Open Licenses for CS via collaborative platforms (LIBER Citizen Science Working Group 2021, 20)
- User-friendly applications for CS experimentation
- Social media for communication of research output (LIBER Citizen Science Working Group 2021, 10)
- Public and private digital services to participate in society (Vuorikari et al, 2016, 8)

3. Challenges and conclusions

The five areas serve as a basis to outline skills and competences that OPUSH project members need to possess or develop to establish OS and especially CS standards. It

can be regarded as a part of the preparation to practice CS experimentation and to ensure everybody a common and life-long learning and an advanced level.

Gaps in existing knowledge of OS and CS skills and competences are apparent, particularly with regard to urban development practitioners and hybrid research infrastructures. Those are involved in the implementation of sustainable urban transformation in multiple ways and can play an essential role in the sustainable development of cities. The OPUSH project takes the already existing knowledge on OS and CS skills as a starting point to deepen this knowledge in the further working steps.

Existing guidelines in this area are primarily addressing the higher education community and citizen scientists. For the OPUSH project, more heterogenic groups are of relevance, especially vulnerable groups of citizens and the practitioners of urban development who are involved in many ways in the implementation of sustainable urban transformation. The following research questions for the further process can be identified in this regard:

- To what extent does the existing knowledge need to be expanded or revised with regard to urban sustainability transformation?
- How can this expanded knowledge be made available to the potentially involved broader target group of CS projects?

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